

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some unsaturated acids by pyridinium bromochromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of maleic, fumaric, crotonic and cinnamic acids by pyridinium bromochromate (PBC) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding epoxide. The reaction is of first order with respect to PBC and the acid. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of these acids was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analyzed by Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. Solvent effect indicated the importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvent. A mechanism involving a three-centre transition state has been postulated.

Keywords : Pyridinium bromochromate, kinetics and mechanism, unsaturated acids.

In continuation of our work on the kinetics and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation of halochromates¹, in the present communication we have reported an investigation of the oxidation of fumaric (FA), maleic (MA), crotonic (CrA) and cinnamic (CiA) acids by PBC (pyridinium bromochromate) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as a solvent. Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Experimental

Materials : The unsaturated acids were commercial products and were used as supplied. PBC was prepared by the reported method and its purity was ascertained by an iodometric method. Solvents were purified as usual. Due to non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Product analysis : Product analysis was carried out with an excess of the reductant over PBC. After completion of reaction (12 h) the solution was treated with an excess (200 cm³) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.46 g (86%) and 2.32 g (81%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP

of acetophenone, acetone and pyruvic acid in the oxidation of cinnamic, crotonic and maleic/fumaric acids respectively. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method, was 3.92 ± 0.06 .

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions, were attained by keeping an excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the reductant over PBC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed at constant temperature (± 0.1 K). The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of PBC spectrophotometrically at 365 nm for at least three half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots of $\log [\text{PBC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs indicated that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was evaluated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{reductant}]$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

Results

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the unsaturated acids studied. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

Stoichiometry : After the workout of the product, the final product, in the oxidation of crotonic, cinnamic,

maleic/fumaric acids is acetone, acetophenone and pyruvic acid respectively. These must have arisen from the corresponding epoxides by rearrangement and decarboxylation as shown in eq. (1).

(R = Ph, Me or COOH)

Epoxies are known to rearrange to ketones. β -Ketoacids readily decarboxylate in acidic solutions². Therefore, the overall oxidation process may be written as follows.

PBC undergoes a two-electron change. This is in accord with our earlier observations with other halochromates¹ also.

The reactions are first order with respect to PBC. Individual kinetic runs were strictly first order in PBC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants do not depend on the initial [PBC]. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of the reactant (Table 1).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of crotonic acid by PBC at 298 K

10^3 [PBC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[CrA] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	5.81
1.00	0.20	11.5
1.00	0.40	23.4
1.00	0.60	34.6
1.00	0.80	46.2
1.00	1.00	57.6
2.00	0.20	12.4
4.00	0.20	11.8
6.00	0.20	12.0
8.00	0.20	11.3
1.00	0.40	23.8 ^a

^acontained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Induced polymerization test : The oxidation of acids in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 2).

Table 2. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen-ion concentration

[Crotonic acid] 0.10 mol dm ⁻³ , [PBC] 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ . Temp. 298 K	[TsOH]/mol dm ⁻³	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}/\text{s}^{-1}$		7.74	9.62	14.0	18.9	22.3	26.6

The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The hydrogen ion dependence has the following form as eq. (3). The values of a and b , for the oxidation of crotonic acid are $5.62 \pm 0.27 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $21.1 \pm 0.45 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($r^2 = 0.9982$).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+] \qquad (3)$$

The rates of the oxidation of the unsaturated acids were obtained in nineteen different organic solvents. The solubility of reagents and reaction of PBC with primary and secondary alcohols limited the choice of solvents. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. Kinetics was similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 4.

The rates of oxidation of the unsaturated acids were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3).

Discussion

Solvent effect : The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (4) of Kamlet *et al.*³

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \qquad (4)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (4), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (5)–(8).

$$\begin{aligned} \log k_2 = & -3.96 + 1.50 (\pm 0.18)\pi^* + \\ & 0.18 (\pm 0.15)\beta - 0.03 (\pm 0.16)\alpha \end{aligned} \qquad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8644; \text{sd} = 0.16; n = 18; \psi = 0.40$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log k_2 = & -3.97 + 1.51 (\pm 0.16)\pi^* + \\ & 0.17 (\pm 0.13)\beta \end{aligned} \qquad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8640; \text{sd} = 0.16; n = 18; \psi = 0.39$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.93 + 1.56 (\pm 0.16)\pi^* \qquad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8500; \text{sd} = 0.16; n = 18; \psi = 0.40$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.08 + 0.44 (\pm 0.33)\beta \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1005; sd = 0.39; n = 18; \psi = 0.97$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter⁴.

Kamlet's³ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 86% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion⁴ the correlation is not even satisfactory [cf. eq. (5)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 85% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation⁵ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also (9).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (9)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (9), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.73 (\pm 0.03)A + 1.55 (\pm 0.02)B - 3.84 \quad (10)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9960; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.51 (\pm 0.51)A - 3.09 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0557; sd = 0.41; n = 19; \psi = 0.99$$

$$\log k^2 = 1.50 (\pm 0.13)B - 3.92 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8834; sd = 0.14; n = 19; \psi = 0.35$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.28 \pm 0.11(A + B) - 3.87 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8947; sd = 0.14; n = 19; \psi = 0.33$$

The rates of oxidation of cinnamic acid in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [cf. eq. (10)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 88% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 89% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 89% of the data, an attempt was made to

correlate rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5306$; $sd = 0.29$; $\psi = 0.70$).

Mechanism :

The observed acid-dependence of the reaction rate may be explained on the basis of a protonation of PBC in a pre-equilibrium (14), with both the protonated and deprotonated forms being active oxidizing species.

The reactions of alkenes with various Cr^{VI} derivatives have been widely studied. The most extensively studied derivative is chromyl chloride. The results of the present study are comparable with those obtained with chromyl chloride.

The low values of the enthalpies of activation indicate that bond-cleavage is not extensive in the formation of the activated complex. The formation of a rigid cyclic activated complex is indicated by the large negative values of the entropies of activation. The probable structures if the activated complex are **1**, **2**, **3** and **4**. **3** is akin to the activated complexes of concerted *cis*-1,3-cycloaddition reactions, which are characterized by values of reaction constants close to zero⁶. Therefore, an activated complex of type **3** is unlikely in view of the fact that the reactions of substituted styrenes and alkenes⁷ exhibit moderately large negative reaction constants (-1.99 and -2.63 respectively).

The reported value of *ca.* -2 in the oxidation of styrenes⁷ by chromyl chloride militates against an activated complex with a fully developed positive charge (**4**). In the present reaction also, replacement of a methyl group by a phenyl group results in a modest rate enhancement (*ca.* 7 times).

A perusal of the relative rates of the oxidation (cf. Table 3) showed that maleic acid is oxidized at a rate *ca.* 3 times that of fumaric acid. This militates against the formation of the activated complex **2**. The formation of a

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of unsaturated acids by PBC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2 / (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
FA	8.82	17.1	29.7	522	42.3 ± 0.4	-157 ± 1	88.8 ± 0.4
CrA	35.1	57.6	96.3	162	36.6 ± 0.7	-166 ± 2	85.7 ± 0.6
MA	26.1	45.0	78.3	135	39.2 ± 0.6	-159 ± 2	86.4 ± 0.5
CiA	180	297	495	828	36.2 ± 0.6	-153 ± 2	81.7 ± 0.5

Table 4. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of crotonic acid by PBC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	20.4	Acetic acid	5.25
1,2-Dichloroethane	22.4	Cyclohexane	0.93
Dichloromethane	19.1	Toluene	5.62
DMSO	57.6	Acetophenone	28.2
Acetone	17.8	THF	9.77
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	34.7	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol ^c	9.12
Butanone	13.5	1,4-Dioxane	11.2
Nitrobenzene	25.7	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	6.51
Benzene	6.92	Carbon disulphide	3.16
Ethyl acetate	3.51		

four-member cyclic activated complex is likely to be more vulnerable to steric factors. Sterically the attack of PBC on the open face of maleic acid (having two hydrogens) is more facile than on fumaric acid. Had the activated complex been a four-membered cyclic structure, the difference in the rates of maleic and fumaric acids would have been much sharper. A formation of even the three-member cyclic activated complex (1) is less hindered in the oxidation of the *cis*-acid as compared to that in the *trans*-acid. However, the data against an involvement of the activated complex 2 is not conclusive. Freeman *et al.*⁷ also have not been able show conclusively whether the activated complex had a three- or a four-member cyclic structure.

The analysis of the solvent effect also supports the proposed mechanism. The fact that the reaction proceeds faster in more polar solvents is in accordance with the formation of a partially charged activated complex from two neutral molecules. The relatively major contribution of the cation-solvating power of the solvents supports the generation of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. Further, the relatively low magnitude of the regression coefficient, *b*, is consistent with the development of a partial positive charge in the activated complex. In the oxidation of benzaldehyde by pyridinium bromochromate¹, where the formation of a carbocationic activated complex has been postulated, the value of *b* is 1.73. To conclude, though both structures 1 and 2 are

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

possible for the activated complex, the balance of evidence is in favour of 1.

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